

What next?

GET IN CONTACT AND REGISTER FOR OUR MAILING LIST TO STAY INFORMED

Both programmes will run from **October 2026** to **September 2027**.

Will you have an ongoing project during the programme timeline?

NO

ScaleDem is not seed funding.

YES

Prepare to apply!

Is your main focus on scaling or on creating/replicating a democratic innovation?

NO

If your goal is only to replicate or launch an innovation, ScaleDem may not be the right fit. However, if you aim to bring innovations to new contexts, methods, or scales, let's have a conversation to clarify this further.

YES

You want to test or adapt a 'scaling process', exploring how your project can grow, deepen, or expand further.

What do you want to do next?

Test new, out-of-the-box ways to scale your project.

Apply to the:

PILOTING PROGRAMME

Address scaling gaps together with others, using proven approaches.

Apply to the:

TWINNING PROGRAMME

Calls open in **December 2025**

Apply by **March 2026**

Follow us and subscribe to our mailing list to receive more information.

Join the Scaling Grounds

Boosting the impact of your democratic project

 scaledem.eu

 ScaleDem

 ScaleDem project

For enquiries: opencalls@scaledem.eu

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For the Pathbreakers

SCALEDEM PILOTING PROGRAMME

Imagine

Experiment

Scale

For the Pioneers

SCALEDEM TWINNING PROGRAMME

Learn

Adapt

Scale

The **ScaleDem Piloting Programme** supports **Pathbreakers**, organisations that already run initiatives which strengthen democracy, directly or indirectly, and who want to **test new ways or places to grow, deepen, or institutionalise** their work. This programme is about **experimentation**, not about starting from scratch but rather about testing that bold “extra idea” to scale your project. We want to support projects that aim to **expand their reach (Scaling Out), strengthen internal capacities (Scaling In), build institutional foundations (Scaling High), and deepen democratic culture (Scaling Deep)** – the four key dimensions of scaling in ScaleDem.

Over **12 months**, selected pilots receive **up to €100,000** and gain access to a European network of peers. This is **not seed funding**, but a **booster**: a unique chance to **test a hunch**.

Who can apply:

Organisations from any sector – **public, private, or civil society** – as well as **consortia or individuals** with an idea ready to scale and relevant experience in facilitating social change.

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Join the **ScaleDem Twinning Programme** if you are a **Pioneer**, an organisation that has already scaled a democratic innovation or wants to **adapt proven approaches** with others. Each **Twinning Community** brings together **one mentor and up to four mentees** for **12 months** of **active coaching, shared learning, and practical, results-oriented action**. These gaps may involve limited reach, weak institutional anchoring, lack of emotional or cultural resonance, or procedural shortcomings, in short, the barriers that prevent democratic innovations from realising their full potential across the four dimensions of scaling explored within ScaleDem.

With **€65,500 per community**, participants **co-design, test, and take measurable steps** to close those gaps. This is **not seed funding**, but a **top-up** for organisations with ongoing projects, offering a structured space to **learn, adapt, and scale together**.

Who can apply:

Organisations from the **public, private, or civil society** sectors, including **local authorities, NGOs, associations, research bodies, or companies**, that are either:

Ongoing project holders

who face or anticipate a scaling gap that could limit their project's full impact (**mentees**).

Experienced practitioners

and scaling advocates keen to share their expertise and support others in adapting scaling processes (**mentors**).

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